

CREATING A CULTURE OF HEALTHY AND REGULAR EATING

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ANNOTATION: This article is written about the formation of a healthy and orderly eating culture, which is becoming one of the global problems of today and is necessary for everyone.

KEYWORDS: proper nutrition, canned goods, fruits and vegetables, parochial nutrition, daily major.

As a person ages, the ability of the digestive organs to process (hydrolyze or break down with enzymes) and absorb food decreases. In order to satisfy the body's need for protein, choose fish and some easily digestible products such as milk, yogurt, sour cream, cheese instead of hard-to-digest meat and meat products, peas, beans, mash. It's better to do it. Moreover, the fat in fish and dairy products is not so dangerous.

It is desirable to reduce as much as possible the consumption of canned food by the elderly. Because the transfer of products (fish, meat, milk and vegetables, fruits, etc.) to the canned state is often carried out in an acidic environment (when the pH indicator is below 7). Chronic consumption of such foods will eventually turn the blood reaction to an acidic side. This condition leads to a number of unpleasant conditions in elderly people (blood clotting, blood-shaped elements sticking to each other and difficult flow through capillary blood vessels, etc.). If you have to eat canned foods, if they are eaten with greens (green onions, chives, cilantro, etc.), the damage of the said acidic environment will be reduced.

It is important to have a variety of daily meals to meet the body's need for all nutrients. For example, instead of eating the same bread all the time, it is more useful for the body to eat bread made from barley, corn, millet, and millet. It is also important to use their leaves and stalks (for example, carrots, beets, etc.) when preparing and eating salads from various greens, vegetables and fruit products. Beetroot leaves contain more minerals and vitamins needed by humans compared to its stem.

The daily intake of 800-900 g of fruits, vegetables and dairy products plays an important role in the rationalization of the diet of the elderly. Although the daily requirement for these products is set to 500-600 g on average, with the aging of the body, in many cases, low absorption of vitamins, minerals and other biologically active substances in the gastrointestinal tract reduces the amount of fruits, vegetables and vegetables. requires multiplication to the specified amount.

It should be said that in the summer and autumn seasons, more of the above-mentioned products are consumed (watermelon, melon, grapes, apples, etc.). But the mentioned index should be reached throughout the year. Especially in the winter and spring seasons, due to a number of objective and subjective reasons, the amount of these products decreases sharply. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to store pumpkin, cabbage, carrots, and turnips and use them widely in daily diet.

Eating in a hurry has a negative effect on the functioning of the digestive organs in the elderly. The point is that the food that has entered the stomach should be eaten when the desire to eat again appears. Otherwise, if there is food in the stomach or when there is no

appetite for food, the normal functioning of the digestive organs is disturbed (digestive juices are not secreted in the appropriate composition and quantity, etc.).

Always eating at a fixed time (breakfast, lunch, dinner) creates a conditioned reflex in relation to time, and digestive juices begin to be released if food is not taken by this time. Movements and sounds (spoon, plate, bowl, noise) made to float food enhance this process and the food is perfectly digested. There is great wisdom in this regard when the great Abu Ali ibn Sina said, "The most harmful thing for the body is to eat again before the food has matured and digested in the stomach."

In order to ensure the health and longevity of every old person, it is important to learn some habits and habits related to eating in youth consumption, etc.) by abstaining from foods containing milk, yogurt, cheese, fish, meat, whole-wheat bread, greens, fruits, berries, vegetables and vegetable products, vegetables should achieve enough fats and at the same time eat eggs, fish caviar, sweets, pastries made with white flour, cakes, bitter tea, and dark coffee in limited quantities .

Lamb, beef, brains, fatty meat, smoked and salted fish, canned food should be consumed in extremely small quantities or not at all, high-strength alcohol should be completely avoided. Adherence to the diet (meal time, amount, fluid intake rules, etc.) is also important for the rationality of the diet of the elderly.

There are many theories about proper nutrition, and new information appears almost every day. Some of them say that it is necessary to limit meat, others say that a diet consisting of only certain products is the key to getting rid of any diseases. In fact, the human body is a very complex system, for its normal functioning it requires both meat and vegetable dishes. Therefore, it is very important to know the rules of proper nutrition. Following dubious recommendations in this regard can cause serious health problems.

First of all, it is necessary to start with making a firm decision about proper nutrition. A few simple rules on which almost all modern dietetics are based and which will help you quickly learn the principles of healthy eating are:

RECIPE

- **Rule 1.** Avoid fast food completely and try not to abuse sweets;
- **Rule 2.** Eat as much as possible from seasonal products - they contain the most nutrients. Winter vegetables and fruits grown in greenhouses or brought from afar, due to the richness of chemicals and long-term storage, not only lose all their useful properties, but also become an accumulator of nitrates and other harmful chemical compounds;
- **Rule 3.** Limit as much as possible the use of refined products: sugar, vegetable oil, white wheat flour, refined white rice. They do not have fiber, which has a negative effect on the digestive system, as well as on the nutrition of the beneficial bacteria living in the intestines. Therefore, instead of white bread, it is better to eat cereal, and instead of refined sugar, it is better to use brown or even honey;
- **Rule 4.** Drink water. Tea, coffee or juices cannot replace water. A person should take at least 30-35 ml of liquid per 1 kg of weight per day. Sweet carbonated drinks are completely prohibited, they contain a very high amount of sugar;
- **Rule 5.** Do not forget about protein foods. They keep a feeling of fullness for a long time and are rich in amino acids. Proteins are necessary for the body to form muscle tissue and renew old cells. Protein-rich foods include a variety of meats, fish, squid, shrimp, nuts, mushrooms, some legumes, eggs, and cottage cheese.

FEEDING PROCEDURE

- **Rule 1.** Adherence to the diet is strictly considered. Eating too little, eating too often or snacking constantly is harmful. It is considered optimal for a healthy person to eat 4-5 times a day, not exceeding 5 hours between meals. If the interval between meals is too long, the metabolism slows down and the body goes into a mode of economy. As a result, body fat

begins to accumulate. In addition, you should not eat in front of the TV or at work, because in this case the brain perceives satiety later;

- **Rule 2.** Eating fresh vegetables and fruits every day. The recommended amount of each is 300 g. In this way, the body will have all the necessary vitamins and fiber. You can also put sliced fruits in a bowl and take them to work or study.

Of course, it is very difficult to immediately and completely change habits and give up a delicious cake with a cup of bitter coffee. It can take a lot of willpower and strength. For this reason, you can eat a sausage sandwich or a cake from time to time. The main thing is that it does not become a daily meal. All products used for food can be conditionally divided into "useful" and "harmful" types. It is recommended to include useful products in the daily diet: they are rich in amino acids, vitamins, micro- and macroelements, fatty acids, fiber. In addition, they are easily digested, do not slow down the metabolism and do not have a harmful effect on health. In addition to proper nutrition, it is necessary to accurately calculate the time of meals, because only timely meals fully compensate for energy consumption. For a healthy person, eating four times a day is the most reasonable. In this case, the load on the digestive system is evenly distributed, food is better digested and absorbed. When eating twice a day with an interval of 7 hours or more, the level of cholesterol in the blood increases, fat begins to accumulate in the body, and the activity of the thyroid gland decreases. In addition, it is often observed that a person eats more than the norm after a long break. Practice shows that two or three days are enough to get used to the chosen routine.

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